

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Partner abbreviations:

- Alleanza Contro il Cancro (**ACC**)
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List of abbreviations

AJCC, American joint committee on cancer
 AML, acute myeloid leukemia
 CHIP, clonal hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential
 CNV, copy number variation

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CRC, colorectal cancer
CRO, contract research organization
dPCR, digital polymerase chain reaction
eCRF, electronic case report form
FFPE, formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded
GL, germline
HM, hematological malignancies
LB, liquid biopsy
LumA, luminal A type breast cancer
MDS, myelodysplastic syndrome
MRD, minimal residual disease
MM, multiple myeloma
MSI, microsatellite instability
MTA/DTA, material and data transfer agreements
NED, no evidence of disease
NGS, next-generation sequencing
NSCLC, non-small cell lung cancer
PBMNC, peripheral blood mononuclear cell
SNV, single nucleotide variant
SOM, somatic
TMB, tumor mutational burden
VAF, variant allele frequency
VUS, variant of unknown significance

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Summary

D24 is the first in a series of three closely related deliverables planned for WP7, which will be released in rapid succession. WP7 established four clinical pilots focused on non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), colorectal cancer (CRC), luminal A type breast cancer (LumA), and hematological malignancies (HM). This approach aims to maximize the capture not only of individual cancer risk, but also familial predisposition or precursor states of overt hematological malignancies. Our work introduces two key novelties: (1) the use of six different biotechnological platforms (and their combined application to test germline DNA, tumor DNA and circulating tumor DNA); (2) an innovative data generation and sharing plan designed to identify unmet needs in EU healthcare. This deliverable reports the successful collection of all clinical and next-generation sequencing (NGS) data, along with preliminary analyses. Key achievements include: (1) a shared electronic case report form (eCRF) and data collection scheme encompassing both clinical and NGS data; (2) Harmonized patient recruitment criteria; (3) Consensus NGS/digital PCR (dPCR) testing platforms; (4) Expanded testing options; (5) Shared evaluation metrics; (6) Open access to expertise within the large CAN.HEAL expert network; (7) A developing dataset of integrated clinical and molecular data; (8) Opportunities for policy implementation across EU Member States (MS). Integrating clinical and NGS data within the collaborative CAN.HEAL framework has yielded valuable lessons in several areas: (a) Harmonization of ethical approval and informed consent procedures; (b) Streamlines data collection and sharing; (c) More efficient resource utilization (avoiding duplication of efforts); (d) A broader range of profiling options for all EU citizens (reducing disparities and promoting equity); and (e) Improved diagnostic and theranostic counseling.

All activities were completed with only minor deviations such as lower-than-expected patient recruitment. Overall, the results align with the objectives set out in the workplan. D24 was submitted on time.

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Objective of the deliverable

- Foreword

This is the first in a series of three closely related deliverables planned for WP7, which will be released in rapid succession. Their order is as follows:

D24: T7.2 - Task leader ICO.

Integration of NGS and clinical data. NGS data available in the framework of clinical information.

Due Jan 31st (**this Deliverable**)

D23: T7.1 - Task leader ACC.

NGS testing data. 40 evaluable patients tested, raw and curated NGS data. Link with ELBS (WP11) to address technical NGS issues.

Due Feb 28th

D25: T7.3 - Task leader NKI-AVL.

Data transfer to WP3 for HTA evaluation.

Due Feb 28th

As the first deliverable from Work Package 7 (WP7), D24 provides an overview of the study plan and completed work, including the essential steps taken to collect clinical information and molecular tumor profiling data, before delving into the integration of next-generation sequencing (NGS) and clinical data—the core focus of this deliverable.

This report introduces the CAN.HEAL clinical pilots, outlining their rationale, primary aims, and logistical framework. On behalf of the entire Consortium, we summarize the process used to identify the relevant pilots, tests, and datasets. We detail the organization of testing and the distribution of tasks within the Consortium. Crucially, we highlight the measures implemented to reconcile diverse clinical settings and individual characteristics, ultimately harmonizing the interpretation of clinical and NGS data. These foundational elements are essential for understanding the integration of clinical and NGS data, the central theme of CAN.HEAL D24.

- WP7 in the context of CAN.HEAL

CAN.HEAL, a collaborative project funded by the EU4Health program, unites 47 partners from 17 MS to bridge the gap between public health and advanced diagnostics, across the entire cancer care continuum. WP7 specifically involves fifteen partners from eight different Countries. Envisioning the future of cancer care in EU, CAN.HEAL addresses all stages, from prevention and early cancer detection/treatment to advanced cancer management. A key focus of CAN.HEAL is the application of NGS and other genomic approaches for molecular tumor profiling. The widespread identification of targetable genetic alterations is crucial to monitor treatment response and has found wide clinical application (1). In the context of the EU Beating Cancer plan (Fig. 1), the CAN.HEAL consortium recognizes that prevention, diagnosis, and treatment should be approached in a concerted way for optimal benefit of patients and citizens.

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In the clinical arm, next-generation sequencing (NGS) and other advanced genomic approaches are being implemented to establish best practices. Our goals are to:

1. Optimize the use of omics technologies in patient care by standardizing data interpretation and facilitating treatment decisions;
2. Establish data-sharing platforms that promote the application of similar diagnostic and therapeutic approaches for patients with comparable cancer profiles across the EU, thereby improving equity;
3. Develop consensus guidelines for molecular tumor profiling and cancer predisposition assessment to improve counseling for family members.

A dedicated clinical work package (WP7, Fig. 2) has been established to address these challenges. WP7 focuses on specific use cases involving colorectal cancer (CRC), non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), luminal A type breast cancer (LumA), and hematological malignancies (HM) associated with clonal hematopoiesis of indeterminate potential (CHIP). For solid tumors, the studies concentrate on young patients with early-stage disease, but with enrichment for those at high risk of progression. As detailed in this deliverable, biological samples, NGS data, clinical-pathological information, and medical imaging data have been prospectively collected and are undergoing retrospective analysis. HM were investigated in patients with myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS), acute myeloid leukemia (AML) and multiple myeloma (MM). To highlight the importance of genetic events in the occurrence and progression of malignancies, we further analyzed the mutational status in 25 MDS and AML patients with clonal evolution at relapse both after chemotherapy and after allogeneic stem cell transplantation. These WP7 clinical pilots are essential to CAN.HEAL's EU-wide data collection efforts.

- The WP7 clinical pilots

WP7 includes four clinical pilot studies focused on NSCLC, CRC, LumA and HM. The first three pilots share several key features: (1) they investigate early-stage cancers (hence potentially curable) in patients with no evidence of disease (NED) as per medical imaging, but poor prognostic indicators (AJCC advanced pathological stages); (2) they enroll patients in the post-operative period and/or adjuvant therapy setting; (3) they involve small sample sizes, *e.g.* 5 to 20 patients per group, with a total of ≥ 40 ; (4) they focus on young patients (≤ 40 or ≤ 50 years depending on the tumor type). This targeted population is designed to maximize the likelihood of identifying both individual and familial risk (*e.g.* familial predisposition). The fourth pilot, concerning HM, deals with conditions that are increasingly recognized as precursors to overt hematological malignancies. Specifically, it examines CHIP, defined as the presence of clonal molecular genetic changes associated with myeloid malignancies in blood or bone marrow cells without signs of HM or cytopenia. Individuals with CHIP display an increased risk of developing HM and cardiovascular diseases.

The CAN.HEAL clinical pilots are all-round initiatives aimed at capturing a spectrum of cancer risk, improving the detection of both individual and familial predispositions. These pilots will establish a shared EU vision for the earliest possible cancer detection. A key component of this work is evaluating

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the feasibility of implementing a standardized set of next-generation sequencing (NGS) strategies to identify genomic alterations in germline, circulating, and tumor DNA. Ultimately, the project aims to develop recommendations for integrating these strategies into the EU health systems, improving patient access to personalized medicine approaches for cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment. Deliverable D24 specifically aims at integrating NGS and clinical data from the distinct pilots.

- Multi-tool wet-lab and dry-lab strategy

The consortium leverages the partners' extensive expertise to utilize a variety of NGS platforms available at the different institutions. A standardized, multi-tool NGS strategy has been implemented for each patient to comprehensively profile genomic alterations across germline DNA (gDNA), tumor DNA (tDNA), and circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA). These alterations, including their trajectories in blood (liquid biopsies, LB), are being rigorously evaluated to identify the most effective tools and metrics for individual patients and to assess the cost-benefit of each intervention. In the context of HM analysis, we explored the potential of ctDNA in enabling comprehensive genetic diagnostics for both early- and late-stage disease. All data, including genetic/genomic information, clinico-pathological data, and medical imaging data, are being shared on a common ICT platform for integrated analysis. This work demonstrates the feasibility and potential of a federated, EU-wide approach to precision oncology trials and its integration into common practice in the near future.

- WP7 pilot design

The diagram in Fig. 3 summarizes the design of the 4 pilots.

The Can.HEAL patient identikit

- young (≤50y; ≤40y breast) - e.g. potential family risk
- early cancer (but high-risk of progression based on stage selection)
- post-operative setting, NED, adjuvant therapy applicable (if in indication)
- gender balance enforced where applicable

Can.HEAL WP7 pre-planned readouts

Use cases

Fig. 3. Clinical pilots at-glance

Major highlights and the Can.HEAL vision behind the pilots are summarized

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All pilots are observational studies involving additional procedures (tissue and blood sampling). No deviation from standard of care assistance/treatment was foreseen based on CAN.HEAL testing results.

The solid tumor pilots are intentionally enriched with patients at high risk of relapse according to AJCC criteria. These patients are also generally younger, increasing the likelihood of identifying genetic predispositions. While endpoints and readouts are similar across different tumor types, specific issues are addressed through dedicated eCRFs and annotation templates. Due to the limited sample size, CAN.HEAL is not designed to definitively assess individual or familial risk in practice. Instead, it focuses on exploring the feasibility of this healthcare model. Conventional formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue sections, whole blood, and plasma were collected at specific time points, i.e. surgery and, for plasma only, at 4, 12, and 24 weeks post-operatively. This plasma collection schedule is based on established protocols for monitoring minimal residual disease (MRD) (2-6).

The HM pilot focuses on patients with AML, MDS or MM associated with CHIP mutations and clonal evolution. All patients were monitored during first-line therapy and remission, as well as in case of relapse or development of secondary tumors. Bone marrow and peripheral blood served as the starting material for all analyses.

All procedures were detailed in a common document, shared and approved by all Partners at the project's outset. These procedures were implemented as planned with only minor deviations. The original protocol and all subsequent amendments were approved by the competent Ethical Committee (see below).

- Patient inclusion criteria

Early Onset (EO)-LUNG (ICO):

Patients with NSCLC (AJCC stages II-III, potentially resectable disease) who were willing to sign the informed consent and to participate. Patients harboring actionable genomic alterations (EGFR, ALK, ROS1, BRAF, KRAS, RET, NTRK, MET, ERBB2, FGFR1-3) and/or younger than 51 years were prioritized for the analysis, since the likelihood of detecting germline alterations in these patients is higher.

Twenty patients were enrolled, as planned.

GerSom (ACC):

Patients with resectable CRC (AJCC stages III-IV) who were willing to sign the informed consent and to participate. Patients younger than 51 years were prioritized for the analysis, since the likelihood of detecting germline alterations in these patients is higher. Most patients were enrolled with NED. They may or may not have received adjuvant therapy. ***Twenty patients were supposed to be enrolled, but only 15 were evaluable*** due to either study withdrawal or poor analyte quality.

LumA (IOV):

Patients with LumA (AJCC stages I-III) who were willing to sign the informed consent and to participate. We gave priority to patients younger than 50 years of age. The patients were enrolled with NED. ***Five patients were enrolled, as planned.***

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CHIP-driven HM (CHAR):

Patients with AML, MDS or MM associated with CHIP who were willing to sign the informed consent and to participate. Although *ten patients were initially planned* for the study, *forty* (20 AML/MDS and 20 MM) *were ultimately enrolled*, all under 50 years of age.

Work performed

- Ethical package design and authorizations by local ethical committees

The CAN.HEAL pilot design was outlined prior to the grant submission, and subsequently refined. The WP7 lead designed an Ethical Board package including a description of the observational study, a synopsis, and an informed consent template. To maintain consistency in the pilot backbone across all recruiting centers (ACC (FPG and IRE) in Italy, ICO in Spain, and IOV in Serbia), the core package (in English) was distributed to each site, ensuring a uniform approach regardless of tumor type, location, or local organization. Each center adapted the core package to meet national regulatory requirements and translated the informed consent form into the local language. A Contract Research Organization (CRO), hired by the WP lead partner (ACC), oversaw all study initiation procedures. The package also included sections on the laboratory manual, data sharing procedures, and GDPR compliance. To expedite patient recruitment, the development of detailed material and data transfer agreements (MTA/DTA) was intentionally deferred and will be reported in the next deliverables in due time.

An initial difference among participating sites emerged in their approaches to fulfilling local ethical requirements. ACC chose to amend an existing protocol (GerSom), which had similar primary aims and a large cohort of young CRC patients. A CAN.HEAL sub-cohort was established within GerSom, with slightly different recruitment criteria and endpoints. Subsequently, a substantial amendment to GerSom was approved to: (a) extend accrual from December 2, 2023, to June 30, 2024, and (b) relax age requirements, allowing the enrollment of a few patients over 50. This six-month extension, which was granted, aligns the pilot duration with the overall CAN.HEAL project extension. It's important to note that the CAN.HEAL pilots were extended not only due to a general realignment of project activities but also because of unforeseen challenges. The most significant of these, affecting all pilots, was the evolution of standard-of-care and treatment guidelines, particularly the introduction of newly approved neoadjuvant regimens, which significantly reduced the pool of potentially eligible patients. In contrast to ACC's approach, ICO and IOV chose to implement their CAN.HEAL pilots as independent projects. While adhering to the general template, these Partners adapted it locally to accommodate the specific characteristics of NSCLC and LumA, respectively. These two pilots were thus conceived and initiated as entirely new projects. Such variation in implementation strategy did not significantly impact the overall study plan.

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CAN.HEAL Milestones: Ethical Committee approvals

GerSom

ACC/FPG: master protocol + specific ACC pilot on CRC approved on 20.03.2023

ACC/IFO: 21.04.2023

ACC/IEO: 27.04.2023

ACC/FPG: amendment/six-month extension, 12.12.2023

EO-lung

ICO 20.04.2023

LumA

IOV: 03.05.2023

HM

CHAR: 03.05.2023

- Clinical samples: collection and sharing

The consortium elected to harmonize the processing/distribution protocol. All clinical specimens were prospectively collected at the clinical sites, aliquoted and stored at local biobanks in a fully certified environment, and then shipped to the laboratories in charge of NGS/dPCR (Fig. 4). Blank FFPE sections (n. 5 + 1 hematoxylin/eosin slide) were stored/shipped at room temperature. Whole blood for GerSom testing was collected in K₂-EDTA tubes and was immediately frozen at -20°C. Plasma for liquid biopsy was collected in Streck (cell-free DNA BCT RUO) tubes to compensate for possible delays/variations in the timing of pre-analytical processing at different centers, and hence variable analyte quality.

Fig. 4. Clinical sample collection, processing, storage and distribution
Preparation was in single-thaw aliquots. Plasma was collected in the exact amount needed for testing

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Blood from Streck tubes was immediately (maximum 24 h) processed by the two-spin protocol (7) at the clinical sites. The technical protocol is summarized in Fig. 5. Cryotubes containing plasma prepared following this protocol were conventionally coded/pseudo-anonymized as detailed in the figure legend, and immediately stored at -80°C in single-use aliquots.

Fig. 5: Can.HEAL plasma processing

Pre-analytical plasma processing of blood obtained for ctDNA testing. Coding was as follows: e.g. CH-CRC-01, 02, 03 etc; CH-EO-LUNG-01, 02, 03 ...; CH-3NBRCa 01. 02. 03 ... w4, w12, and w24 was added to each of the four plasma samples to identify timing, e.g. CH-CRC-01sur, CH-CRC-01w4, CH-CRC-01w12, CH-CRC-01w24, etc

Once collected and processed, clinical specimens were dispatched to the specific labs with the appropriate expertise for the different wet-lab tools. Blood and plasma were shipped in dry ice. No freeze-thawing was allowed. A detailed flowchart and each partner’s role in the project are shown in Fig. 6. Compliance with the procedures outlined in the laboratory manual was consistently high across all sites, and the sample dispatch plan operated effectively, with the minor exception of a small number of samples lost during shipment.

Fig. 6: Can.HEAL WP7: Partners roles and specimen/data flowchart

Biological specimens and data collected by the clinical pilot centers were shipped to the laboratories in charge of NGS testing. NGS results and clinical-pathological-imaging data are being electronically annotated by the originators on the shared database for subsequent analysis. Can.HEAL WP7 Partners in charge/involved of/in each step are indicated.

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- Testing

Fig. 7. CanHEAL pilots, clinical samples, and NGS tools
The pilots envisage 6 wet lab tools/approaches.

The pilots took advantage of 6 wet-lab tools available to the Partners (Fig. 7). Five of these approaches (mostly based on NGS) were systematically applied to all patients with solid tumors (n. 1 to 5), whereas HM followed a dedicated testing pathway. The data were structured to be recorded in a c-Bioportal–based central platform, as described (8).

GerSom (<https://www.alleanzacontroilcancro.it/en/progetti/GerSom/>), is a targeted NGS panel designed to test both tDNA and gDNA. All other tools employed are optimized for ctDNA analysis, reflecting CAN.HEAL's emphasis on minimally invasive approaches. The HM tool is an exception, as it also incorporates DNA from bone marrow.

GerSom detects oncogenic drivers, actionable alterations, multi-gene biomarkers such as tumor mutational burden (TMB) and microsatellite instability (MSI) in tDNA, along with pharmacogenomics variants and germline variants associated with the risk to develop cancer (Fig. 8). GL variants were referred to genetic counseling. In the specific CAN.HEAL context, GerSom was applied to detect index alterations in tissues to be subsequently tested by dPCR to detect MRD.

Fig. 8. GERSOM diagnostics: targeted NGS to capture cancer drivers in both the germ line and somatic tumor DNAs

Gersom is a unified NGS tool to capture germline (risk) and somatic (predictive/prognostic) information. The size of the panel, versatility, and the many areas where the panel is applicable are highlighted.

MRD-dPCR testing builds on individual tumor-specific single nucleotide variants (SNVs). These may be considered tumor ‘fingerprints’, and were tested in blood by highly customized, ultrasensitive dPCR assays (7). Tumor-informed liquid biopsy is currently considered the most extensively validated method to detect MRD at an early stage (9) (Fig. 9).

- dPCR custom-designed (bespoke) assays for ultra-sensitive (MRD detection) testing of SNVs captured by NGS fingerprinting intDNA.

Fig. 9. dPCR for ctDNA testing

Several in-house NGS panels were directly developed by members of the CAN.HEAL consortium with their own resources. These implement ground-breaking metrics that are presently under investigation worldwide for their potential to detect MRD and predict disease progression. For instance, EKUT developed ^{CH3}DNA, a methylome-based approach to detect epigenetic cancer alterations.

IC implemented a custom NGS panel known as DRAGON (Detection of Relevant Alterations in Genes involved in Oncogenetics by NGS), commercially available as SureSelect CD Curie CGP by Agilent. The panel examines 571 cancer-related genes, relevant for diagnosis, prognosis, and targeted therapy. It explores both the nucleotide sequence and copy number variations (homozygous deletions and focal amplifications). The assay employs probes targeting these 571 genes along with a whole-genome backbone of probes at an average resolution of one probe per 200 Kb. This comprehensive approach

enables the determination of ploidy, estimated cellularity, and a detailed genomic profile for each chromosome.

GIPXplore (Fig. 10) is a bioinformatic pipeline created by KUL that is based on unsupervised clustering analysis and supervised machine-learning workflow. This pipeline is an affordable and cost-effective machine-learning pipeline for ctDNA profiling using low-pass sequencing data, which enables simultaneous accurate multi-cancer detection and cancer-type prediction (10).

Fig. 10. GIPXplore: cfDNA fragmentomic patterns from cancer patients have a differential genome-wide distribution compared to healthy ones (green and blue profiles respectively). Mining the patterns of shallow WGS cfDNA from cancer patients can provide a minimally invasive approach to (early) cancer detection via the analysis of a blood draw. GIPXplore is a bioinformatic pipeline based on unsupervised clustering analysis and supervised machine learning workflow to analyse liquid biopsy samples and to improve (pan)cancer detection. Concurrently, classifiers are constructed to predict disease status and identify disease types to assess the use of such transformed genome-wide features as a marker for diagnostic application (Che et al., 2022).

Finally, CHIP, *i.e.* a condition associated with the risk to develop HM (11-17), was revealed by NGS panels. For AML, ctDNA analysis from bone marrow aspirates provides valuable information, enabling the identification of mutations and rearrangements critical for diagnosis. The use of ctDNA offers clear advantages for assessing minimal residual disease. Liquid biopsy holds greater promise for MM, demonstrating potential in both early, pre-symptomatic stages and later stages of disease progression. At the onset of the disease, AML/MDS patients were screened using a myeloid NGS panel, which likely includes common mutations. Some of these are often associated with CHIP and the development of leukemia. In MM patients, a liquid biopsy was performed using the comprehensive TSO Pan-Cancer panel, which covers a broader spectrum of mutations across different cancer types. This approach aims to identify both typical myeloma mutations, as well as CHIP-related mutations that might influence disease progression.

- Clinical and NGS information

An effort was made to design a common eCRF backbone, which is presently being evaluated to determine its effectiveness in integrating clinical and molecular data.

The CAN.HEAL eCRF includes the following data fields:

Demographics and info:

- Gender
- Date of birth
- Family history of cancer in 1st (siblings, parents, offspring) and 2nd degree relatives (parents' siblings, grandparents), possibly with age at diagnosis
- Previous diagnosis of a cancer predisposing syndrome in the patient and/or family (if available provide gene/mutation)
- Tobacco smoker (lung cancer)
- Pseudoanonymization code (*e.g.* CH-CRC-01 ... CH-NSCLC-01), and associated clinico-pathological/NGS data

Clinical pathological info:

- Pathological diagnosis
- AJCC TNM staging
- Neoadjuvant treatment (if any) and duration
- Adjuvant treatment (if any) and duration

Molecular info (pre-existing):

- Non-CAN.HEAL NGS testing – GL (name of test from a dropdown)
- Non-CAN.HEAL NGS testing – SOM (name of test from a dropdown)
- Known GL variant(s): gene, position, fusion partners, *etc.*
- VAF/CNV of above, if applicable
- Known tDNA (SOM) variant(s): gene, position
- VAF/CNV of above, if applicable
- Known ctDNA molecular alterations (if known)
- VAF/CNV of above, if applicable
- cfDNA fragment size
- cfDNA mean deduplicated depth

CAN.HEAL wet-lab specific info:

- Whole blood drawn (ml) for GL, isolation of PBMCs for CHIP/MBL pilot
- Total GL DNA available and concentration (indicate buffer) after extraction (GL)
- Total tDNA available and concentration (indicate buffer) after extraction (SOM)
- Blood for LB; use of Streck (cfDNA BCT RUO) tubes: Y(recommended)/N
- Available plasma aliquots and their sizes

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- Freezing-80°C (Y/N)
- Freezing at suboptimal temperatures (free text for annotation)

Results of testing with CAN.HEAL tools:

- DNA (GL) variants (pathogenic, unknown, VUS)- list
- DNA pharmacogenomic-relevant variants – list
- tDNA (SOM) tumor-specific variants- list
- VAF/CNV of above
- cfDNA variants (list) and AF
- cfDNA % methylation per region
- VAF/CNV of above
- CHIP/MBL (list)
- Additional customized biomarkers, fragmentomics (GIPXplore)

Results

We report testing results separately for the 4 pilots.

- The NSCLC cohort (ICO)

Data from n=20 patients with NSCLC were collected at ICO. Median age was 65 (39-79) and 60% were males. Most patients were former smokers (65%), followed by current smokers (25%) or never smokers (10%). The most common histological type was lung adenocarcinoma (75%), followed by squamous cell carcinoma (20%) and large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma (5%). Five patients received neoadjuvant therapy (consisting in 3 cases of chemoimmunotherapy, while 15 patients undergo upfront surgery). At most patients were alive (85%) and only 3 patients experienced tumor recurrence at the last data cutoff. In-house NGS data were available in only 50% of patients. Nevertheless, they were included for comparison with GerSom. The most recurrent mutated oncogene was KRAS, seen in 4 patients (G12C, n=2; G12V, n=1; G12R & G12A), followed by EGFR in 2 patients (exon 19 and L858R). Most specimens were analyzed using the OncoPrint Precision Assay platform. A summary of ICO patients may be found in annex 1. It is evident at glance that the dataset contains patients who underwent progression and/or have index mutations, confirming appropriateness of the data/NGS collection plan as originally designed. This dataset is therefore informative.

- The CRC cohort (ACC)

Data from n=15 patients were collected. In these samples (locally available at ACC affiliated entities), GerSom sequencing is completed. ACC found of interest to explore a new pipeline for the bioinformatic identification of the SNVs most promising to reveal MRD. Tumor tissue and matched normal genomic DNA were sequenced using the ACC GerSom AmpliSeq-based panel. Variant calling was performed using the Torrent Variant Caller (TVC) pipeline, applying low-stringency somatic parameters to ensure comprehensive detection. The resulting VCF files were automatically uploaded to the platform developed by ACC for centralized data retention, access and analysis. This platform

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allows automatic variant annotation, prioritisation and filtering to generate a short report with relevant variants. More specifically, the centralized reporter processes these files using an internally developed bioinformatics pipeline at IEO – ACC. This pipeline integrates multiple annotation and prioritization tools, including GATK Funcotator for functional classification, and ANNOVAR, InterVar, ReNOVO, and CancerVar for variant prioritization. Additionally, ESCAT classification is provided where applicable.

To refine the list of candidate variants, a series of automated filtering steps are applied. Variants are retained only if they meet specific criteria, such as sufficient sequencing coverage ($\geq 50x$) and relevant genomic localization. Variants in non-coding regions (*e.g.*, introns, UTRs, intergenic regions) are generally excluded unless classified as pathogenic or of uncertain significance by at least one of the annotation tools. Additionally, only variants with a somatic VAF greater than 0.05 or a germline VAF greater than 0.2 are considered for further analysis.

Following this automated filtering, the generated tables undergo a manual curation process. The goal of this final step is to identify and prioritize up to three of the most relevant genomic alterations for each patient. These selected variants are then used to design patient-specific assays, which will enable the detection and monitoring of tumor-derived alterations in blood plasma over time.

In the first seven patients analyzed from the ACC CRC cohort, at the end of the bioinformatic pipeline, we detected from 2 to 30 independent, tumor-specific SNVs (median = 13) (see Annex 2), from which at least 3 index alterations will be prioritized to be monitored by bespoke dPCR. Thus, we have generated a bioinformatic pipeline that is key to integrate tDNA, ctDNA and clinical data.

- **The LumA cohort (IOV)**

Data from five female patients with Luminal A type breast cancer (LumA) were collected at IOV. The median age was 46 years (range: 39–50). Three patients were non-smokers, and two were smokers. Two patients received adjuvant therapy, and all patients underwent radiotherapy after surgery. At the time of data analysis (January 2025), all patients were alive with no signs of recurrence. Analysis of these samples is in progress.

- **The HM cohort (CHAR)**

Data from forty patients were collected, 20 AML/MDS and 20 MM, all under 50 years of age and whose disease was associated with CHIP. Patients were followed both during first-line therapy and complete remission, and at disease relapse or development of second tumors. Both common MM mutations and CHIP mutations were identified, suggesting that CHIP may play a role in clonal evolution or exist as a concurrent feature in these patients.

- **Summary of NGS testing in the context of clinical data**

In summary, preliminary results from the pilots clearly demonstrate the feasibility of integrating diverse techniques, study plans, and site-specific implementation logistics. Effective integration of clinical and NGS data has been achieved. While liquid biopsy data require further analysis, conclusive findings will be presented in subsequent reports, notably deliverable D25.

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Main achievements

Main achievements relevant to D24 are:

1. A shared electronic case report form (eCRF) and data collection scheme encompassing both clinical and NGS data
2. Harmonized patient recruitment criteria
3. Common NGS/dPCR testing platforms
4. Expanded testing options
5. Shared evaluation metrics
6. Open access to expertise within the large CAN.HEAL expert network
7. A developing dataset of integrated clinical/molecular data to optimize:
 - Evidence-based logical deduction and clinical decision processes
 - Opportunities for policy implementation across EU MS.

Impact

Complete integration of clinical and NGS data requires further time, as ctDNA testing is still in progress; at the time of writing, only tDNA testing has been completed. Despite this limitation, several lessons were learnt from the collaborative CAN.HEAL effort, each of which has implications for achieving more comprehensive integration of clinical and molecular data. In summary:

1. Significant progress was made in streamlining procedures for obtaining ethical approval and informed consent. CAN.HEAL demonstrates the need for, and the feasibility of, harmonizing trial enrollment procedures across the EU. Multi-center studies encompassing diverse neoplastic conditions can be effectively conducted by establishing pre-defined criteria a priori and developing a continuous process of expert consensus.
2. Recruitment was largely successful. Clinical and NGS data have been collected, and further steps are underway to ensure GDPR-compliant federated data analysis (as will be detailed in D23 and D25).

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3. The successful collection of clinical and NGS data represents a significant achievement and was essential for generating data suitable for integration even when generated on different platforms. The preliminary data exchange described in this report clearly demonstrates the feasibility of establishing a common framework for capturing genetic and individual risk of disease progression.
4. The CAN.HEAL partners recognized that a shared common vision is equally important as having access to innovative molecular metrics in the context of clinical data. To our knowledge, CAN.HEAL represents the first concerted effort toward this goal. If successful, the CAN.HEAL model has the potential to promote more efficient resource allocation by avoiding duplication of efforts, expanding access to a wider range of profiling options for all EU citizens, thereby reducing disparities and promoting equity, and improving diagnostic and theranostic counseling.

All activities were completed with only minor deviations such as lower-than-expected patient recruitment. Overall, the results align with the objectives set out in the workplan. D24 was successfully submitted on time.

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Annex 1. Representative integration of clinical and NGS data (source EO-lung, ICO)

Code	Age	Gender	Tobacco	AP	NGS	Actionable alterations	TMB	Strategy	pTNM	Comments	Status	Recurrence
CN-NSCLC-01	60	M	Former	ADC		KRAS G12R & STK11 c.388G>T (A2) and KRAS G12A & STK11 c.580G>T & ATM c.967A>G	12,6 mut/Mb	S-Adj CT	pT2b(m)N0	2 lesions	Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-02	66	F	Former	ADC	ND			S-Adj CT	pT1bpN0		Alive	No
CN-NSCLC-03	68	M	Former	ADC	OPA		ND	S-Adj CT	pT2apN0		Alive	No
CN-NSCLC-04	79	F	Former	ADC	OPA	KRAS G12V	ND	Surgery	pT2apN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-05	60	M	Current	ADC	OPA	KRAS G12C	ND	NA CT-S	ypT1cpN2		Alive	suspected
CN-NSCLC-06	62	M	Current	ESC	ND			Surgery	pT1cpN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-07	64	M	Current	ADC	ND			Surgery	pT1mipN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-08	79	M	Former	ADC	ND			Surgery	pT1cpN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-09	70	M	Former	ADC	ND			Surgery	pT1cpN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-10	59	F	Never	ADC	ND			Surgery	pT1bpN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-11	72	M	Current	ESC	ND			NA CTIO-S	ypT1bpN1		Death	no
CN-NSCLC-12	58	M	Former	ADC	OPA	BRAF G469V		NA CTIO-S	ypT1bypN0.		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-13	70	F	Former	ADC	OPA	EGFR L858R & TP53 c.820G>T		Surgery	pT4pN2		Alive	yes
CN-NSCLC-14	73	M	Former	ESC	ND	ND		NA CTIO-S	ypT1a ypN1		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-15	78	M	Former	ESC	ND			Surgery	pT3pN0		Death	no
CN-NSCLC-16	61	F	Former	ADC	OPA	KRAS G12C		NA CT-S	ypT3 ypN2 + ypTis		Death	yes
CN-NSCLC-17	70	M	Current	LCNEC+SCLC				Surgery	pT1b pN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-18	63	F	Former	ADC	ND			Surgery	pT1bN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-19	39	F	Never	ADC	OPA			Surgery	pT2a pN0		Alive	no
CN-NSCLC-20	55	F	Former	ADC	OPA	EGFR L746_A750		Surgery	pT2apN2		Alive	yes

Annex 2. Representative NGS data from the CRC cohort (source GerSom, ACC)

ID	pathogenic/likely pathogenic	uncertain significance	benign/likely benign	TOTAL
filtered.GERS26BVAA-2TAD126.xlsx	5	4	8	17
filtered.GERS26D0S5-2TAD126.xlsx	1	5	7	13
filtered.GERS26KLL0-2TAD126.xlsx	1	4		5
filtered.GERS26N9FG-2TAD126.xlsx	4	7	10	21
filtered.GERS26V0U3-2TAD126.xlsx	3	1	1	5
filtered.GERS262K3Z-2TAD126.xlsx	7	14	9	30
filtered.GERS2678ML-2TAD126.xlsx		2		2